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Promoting the Right Relationship with Others through Mathematics Teaching-Learning

Abstract: Human beings are fundamentally relational and social beings, and our meaningful existence is possible through living in a community. This, in turn, entails that we need to relate to others properly to have a peaceful and harmonious existence. Considering all the negativities plaguing human society today, it has become crucial to promote the right relationship with others from a very young age. It can be done by educating the heart of the learners through imparting values like justice, love, compassion, respect, equality, tolerance, and others. Often mathematics teaching-learning has been limited to the cognitive level, and very seldom concerns of relationship with others, affective dimensions, and values are brought up in mathematics classrooms. More and more mathematics educators recommend mathematics education to assume a bigger responsibility for transforming the world. In this article, I explore how mathematics teaching-learning may promote proper relationships among learners through the various mathematics topics they learn. This will be done by an autoethnographical reflection on my lived experiences of mathematics as a student and teacher as well as on the writings of various scholars. I also share some of my experiments of connecting mathematics teaching-learning to values that promote the right relationship with others.

Keywords: Mathematics teaching-learning, autoethnographical, relationship with others, educating the heart, imparting values, connecting, lived experiences

Introduction

The next Buddha will not take the form of a person.

The next Buddha will rather take the form of a community, a community that practices understanding and loving-kindness, a community that practices mindful living.

This may be the most important thing for the survival of the earth.

(Thich Nhat Hanh)

In the past few years, my area of interest has been relationships-responsible mathematics teaching-learning. I have been exploring how mathematics teaching-learning can be connected to human beings' fundamental relationships with the Cosmos, self, Sacred, and others, instead of confining it as a mere head-level cognitive

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activity. My reflections on the negativities and paradoxes that humanity faces today resulted in an understanding that they are signs of a breakdown in our relationships with the Cosmos, self, Sacred, and others. I believe that when persons live in harmony with the others, nature, Sacred and oneself, they become integral persons (Pope Francis, 2013). As integral persons, we understand that our own well-being is inseparable from the well-being of others, and this well-being depends on how we relate to the wider community (Luitel & Taylor, 2019; Miller, 2002; O'Sullivan & Taylor, 2004). We will be able to transform ourselves into a community that practices understanding, loving-kindness, and mindful living.

Being a mathematics educator, I was curious to discover how mathematics teaching-learning can promote integral living and the well-being of the wider community by helping learners to enhance these relationships. In the process, I joined the Master of Philosophy (MPhil) in Mathematics Education at Kathmandu University. As an MPhil student, I explored the various dimensions of mathematics teaching-learning. I conducted an autoethnographical inquiry for my dissertation in which I delved more into relationships-responsible mathematics teaching-learning in my life as a student and teacher. This article is a glimpse into my autoethnographical exploration of connecting mathematics teaching-learning to the relationship with others. I start by justifying why I chose an autoethnographical research lens.

My Choice of Autoethnography as a Method

I wanted my research to be a personal transformational process. I wanted to rethink and revise my life as a mathematics educator and to make conscious decisions about who and how I want to be as a mathematics educator (Custer, 2014). I discovered that autoethnography is transformative in nature and would benefit me tremendously. The transformative benefits of autoethnography are explicated by Custer (2014) in the following manner. "Autoethnography is a transformative research method because it changes time, requires vulnerability, fosters empathy, embodies creativity and innovation, eliminates boundaries, honors subjectivity, and provides therapeutic benefits" (p. 11). Consequently, I felt that autoethnography could become a tool for me for self-knowing and awakening, healing, empowering, challenging, and overcoming.

Other essential characteristics of autoethnography as a method are given by Jones et al. (2013) in the following words. "Autoethnography is not simply a way of knowing about the world; it has become a way of being in the world, one that requires living consciously, emotionally, reflexively" (as cited in Custer, 2014, p.1). They further add that doing autoethnography entails a thorough examination of our lives, thoughts, deeds, feelings, and words. According to them, it is an interrogation of one's beliefs and assumptions, digging further into our deepest fears and insecurities. It helps us to "rethink and revise our lives, making conscious decisions about who and how we want to be. And in the process, it seeks a story that is hopeful, where authors ultimately write themselves as survivors of the story they are living" (as cited in Custer, 2014, p. 1).

Further, "Autoethnography humanizes research by focusing on life as "lived through" in its complexities; showing that you as readers and we as authors matter; and demonstrating to others who are involved in or

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implicated by our projects that they matter, too" (Adams, Ellis & Jones, 2017, p. 8). "Autoethnography is an approach to research and writing that seeks to describe and systematically analyze (graphy) personal experience (auto) in order to understand cultural experience (ethno)" (Ellis et al., 2011, p. 273). In autoethnography, the self is put at the center of the cultural analysis as it is a reflective narration of the experiences of the self in a particular context. According to Chang (2007), autoethnography must "transcend mere narration of self to engage in cultural analysis and interpretation" (as cited in Ellis et al., 2011, p. 43). The autoethnographical approach enables us to "examine our own practice, separately and together, within the context of the larger social, cultural and political ethos in which we live and work" (Kress & Frazer-Booth, 2016, p. 107). It thus enhances cultural understanding of the self and others and enables the transformation of the self and others. It offers the researchers opportunities to connect with their outside world and understand it empathetically and compassionately (Bonghanoy et al., 2019; Belbase, 2019).

King Miller (2020) talks about the power of autoethnographical writing, and I discovered it during my writing. It was not easy to enter into an academic inquiry and write about my experiences in a way that made sense to my research topic. It was unnerving and challenging and at the same time, invigorating. As I started the journey, I realized that writing too was a spiritual journey and transformative in many ways. While writing down my experiences, I began to recognize that they made more sense and meaning when expressed in writing and enabled me to delve further into my thoughts and feelings. Writing provoked new questions about myself and the subject of my inquiry, belief systems, and unchallenged assumptions, while ensuring that my inquiry is "grounded, contextual and rhizomatic." I also experienced the evoking of "deeper parts of the self, heal wounds, enhance the sense of self" and it affected my identity as a mathematics educator (Richardson, 2000, p.11). Below, I share the autoethnographic narratives of my experiences of mathematics and relationship with others.

Musings on My Mathematical Experiences

Human beings are social and relational beings. One of the distinguishing features of human beings is the capacity to live in a community. This requires a human being to relate to others properly to have harmonious living. Relationship with others is a quintessential aspect of human existence. If so, should not mathematics also be concerned about this relationship? How can mathematics be taught so that students learn to relate appropriately with others? When persons are guided by values of love, justice, peace, and compassion, they can relate to others in the right manner. What is the role of mathematics in promoting such values among students?

During my MPhil journey, I mused a lot about my life as a mathematics student and teacher along the lines of the aforementioned questions. This critical and introspective journey was a transformative process as a mathematics teacher-learner, especially in my worldview of mathematics teaching-learning. My awakening was further deepened during the writing of my research paper as it opened my eyes to a world of possibilities in mathematics. I realized that it was possible for mathematics teaching-learning to be connected to the lives

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of all concerned, especially to the four fundamental relationships of every human being with the Sacred, the Cosmos, the self, and others.

In the various chapters of my inquiry, I critically looked at my life as a student and teacher to see if these relationships were part of my teaching-learning of mathematics. My mathematics engagement, by and large, as a student and teacher neither helped me to become an integral person nor my learners. These relationships were essential parts of my life and my students' lives, but not in my mathematics classes, which mainly focused on their little world of formulae, steps, memorization, solving problems, scoring marks, etc. It remained at the head level and had nothing much to do with the other dimensions – their heart, soul/spirit, and social and emotional. It was disconnected from these critical dimensions of life and had severe damaging consequences. One such consequence was in the relationship with the others (Varghese, 2019).

As a student and teacher, I experienced mathematics mainly as a subject dealing with the cognitive dimension alone. It was mere academics and intellectual. There was a syllabus to be taught, a course to be covered, and a textbook to be used. As long as the students knew how to solve problems, memorize the formulas, and follow the processes, students were considered to be good in mathematics. It was not just my experience; it seems to be the general experience worldwide. As Seah et al. (2016) have mentioned, "For years, school mathematics curricula have been dominated by a focus on skills and techniques: to many students, mathematics is something you do, rather than something you think about, imagine, argue, or feel" (p. 14). Elsewhere, we read that mathematics is not considered a subject that also deals with a person's affective dimension (Bishop et al., 2003).

When I look back at my life learning mathematics at the school and university levels, I noticed that I used mathematics for many purposes but mostly ignorantly without recognizing any connection to other dimensions. It was primarily utilitarian. Further, I do not remember any of my teachers trying to impart anything other than intellectual stuff in the mathematics classroom. There were no attempts to connect it to the social, emotional, spiritual, or ecological dimensions of my life. They never took me beyond the mathematical concepts. It was merely bookish, except perhaps for a handful of teachers. In this regard, the following questions arose in my mind. 'Was I only a rational/cognitive being as a student? Was I not relational too? Shouldn't mathematics be concerned with my relationships with the self, others, cosmos, and the Sacred?' What about my other intelligences that are mentioned by Huitt (2011)?

In school mathematics, we establish and deal with various relationships using the symbols like plus, minus, division, multiplication, brackets, equality, and non-equality. As I reflect on it now, learning about them could also have been fitting occasions to instill values that sustain relationships with others. In order to have consistency in any mathematical system, the above symbols have to be used/placed properly. Likewise, in human relationships too, values, attitudes, behavior that support relationships have to be proper. They function like mathematics symbols in establishing and sustaining relationships and giving them consistency. The framework of human society is based on these values, and without them, no human society can survive.

Think about the equality and non-equality signs. In a world filled with disparity and where the rich-poor gap is growing, mathematics classes on equality and non-equality signs would be ideal occasions to have

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discussions on them. Further, those would have been occasions to ask questions like, "Is a man superior to a woman?" "Does a rich man have more privileges than a poor man?" "What makes me inferior or superior to another person?" "Is there a basis for me to treat everyone as an equal?" Unfortunately, none of this happened in my school days. It was just mathematical concepts. As a result, my thinking often remained at the head level as in the following incident during my university days.

I was getting ready to leave after visiting my home during my college days. As I was bidding goodbye, my father reached into the table drawer and handed me a bunch of coins. I was reluctant to take them. After all, they were coins, and I had sufficient money with me for the travel.

So I said, "I have enough money for now. What will I do with all these coins"? He replied, "They are not meant for you. They are meant for the beggars who come to the train. You must always give them all something." Here was my father, who had never traveled by train, advising me. I said, "Most of them are not deserving, and they just pretend that they have nothing. They are all a nuisance in the train as many of them indulge in stealing." He said, "I know all that. It is true that some of them are cheats, some are a nuisance, and so on. But the fact that they are begging indicates a truth that we do not understand. We must always give them something. How can you know for sure who is deserving and who is not."

I did not say much after that. I took the coins and put them in the outer pocket of my bag. As I was traveling, I thought about those incidents when I had pretended that I did not see a beggar or ignored one deliberately during my many journeys, busying myself in a book or newspaper. Ignoring the presence of someone must be the worst form of disrespect for a person's dignity.

My mathematical head was not trained for looking at the beggars from such a perspective. Here was my father connecting his head, heart, and hand and telling me to do the same instead of remaining in my head alone. I was being taught an important lesson about "what we know" must affect and have a connection to "what we feel" and "what we do" (Gazibara, 2013, p. 75). That was the beginning of a change of heart in me about how I looked at beggars and anyone else in need and how I responded to them. I was not too quick to judge them thereafter but offered whatever help I could. Even if I could not help them, I would never ignore them. I would at least say that I was not in a position to help them and thus always acknowledge their presence.

Linear algebra was a major paper in my university studies. When we learned about the concepts of sets, groups, rings, and so on, the notions of belonging and identity were essential. We learned about the properties that make an element belong to a set, group, or ring, what makes an element an insider, and what makes an element an outsider. Functions and relations were other concepts we elaborately dealt with at the tertiary level. What would have been a better opportunity than such concepts to talk about human relationships? Such lessons would have been ideal platforms to talk about healthy and proper relationships, values that sustain such relationships, and things that harm relationships. I wonder if talking about such things in class would have tainted the purity of mathematics?

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We visited a tribal village during my university studies as part of our rural immersion program. It was situated many kilometers from the city. As expected, many of my city-grown classmates found the whole experience strange. For some, it was an eye-opener, whereas, for others, it was difficult and disgusting. The primary purpose of our trip was to find out more about the life struggles of those tribal people. As in many other parts of India, they too were victims in the name of development and integration into the mainstream.

Consequently, they were losing their land and livelihood, their connection with the forest, and their culture and tradition contaminated with harmful elements of modernity. The persons working with and for them were concerned about this loss of identity and the eventual disappearance of the entire tribal society itself. We all listened to these concerns, visited some of the villages and houses, saw the peril of many of them, and had a little first-hand experience of their lifestyle in those two days.

We got back to the city and to our classrooms a few days later after some rest. In the classrooms, there was no discussion whatsoever regarding what we experienced in the village. 'Hope you all had a good time' was the only thing our teachers mentioned. We friends discussed the fun and other experiences that we had there. A few of us did talk for a few days about the life of the tribal people with a lot of sympathy. But that was it. It slowly got overwhelmed by complex analysis, integral calculus, modern algebra, topology, and whatnot.

In retrospect, the trip was a great occasion to read the lives of the tribal people with mathematics. It was a chance for us to understand the equations that initially defined their lives and how such equations were changing due to the so-called integration into the mainstream. However, reading the world with mathematics or the notion of social justice had not entered into the teaching pedagogy in those days (Gutstein, 2003). As a result, it never occurred to us students as well. We ended up as mere visitors, our experiences of the struggles of the people there having nothing to do with our apparent mathematical life.

Lessons Learned from Others

My interest in the topic of connecting mathematics to the relationship with others took an upward tangent as I delved into the writings of others. As the courses of MPhil began to unfold, reading articles and books related to it began to be part of my life. I began to see how many others perceived the relationship to others in the teaching-learning of mathematics and gained tremendous insights. The great Greek philosopher Aristotle once said, "Educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all." Likewise, Martin Luther King (1947) expressed, "Intelligence plus character – that is the goal of true education" (p. 124). I began to understand that promoting the right relationships with others in teaching-learning is a way to educate the heart.

I believe that the education of the heart is not about what is taught (subject matter) but what it does to both the teacher and the learner. As a result, we talk about holistic education, humanist education and citizenship education, and the like. The essence of them, I feel, is summarized by Cohen (2006) in the following manner. "Along with an informed citizenry, a democratic society must reflect a respect for others, an ability to

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collaborate, regard for fairness and justice, concern for the commonwealth, as well as voluntary, active participation in society" (p. 203). Therefore, the purpose of education is not merely to produce informed citizens who are educated only in mind.

Recent educational theories like Social and Emotional Learning, Social, Emotional and Ethical Theories (Cohen, 2006; Khatib et al., 2013; Elias, 2006) emphasize caring for others, showing empathy, respecting others, learning to make sound decisions, appreciating diversity, developing good moral/ethical character as essential objectives of education. All these theories promote values that help one's relationship with others and the need for educators to impart such values to students through their teaching. We also hear a lot about affective education. Citing Moskowitz, Khatib et al. (2013) have this to say. "Affective education is effective education. It works on increasing skills in developing and maintaining good relationships, showing concern and support for others, and receiving these as well. It is a special type of interaction in itself, consisting of sharing, caring, acceptance, and sensitivity" (p. 47).

Elsewhere, Berman (1990) talks about social responsibility and social consciousness in education. He says,

Social responsibility – that is, a personal investment in the well-being of others and of the planet - doesn't just happen. It takes intention, attention, and time. It may even take redesigning schools and classrooms to embrace a culture that values and creates empowerment, cooperation, compassion, and respect. Educating young people for social consciousness means posing a set of questions like what does the way I lead my life mean for the lives of others? How can I contribute in a meaningful way to creating a more just, peaceful, and ecological sound society? (p.75).

Global citizenship education is another theory that considers the education of the heart as necessary. UNESCO defines the primary aim of Global Citizenship Education (GCED) as "nurturing respect for all, building a sense of belonging to a common humanity and helping learners become responsible and active global citizens." Along similar lines, Margaret Hepworth (n.d.), the founder of The Gandhi Experiment, defines global citizenship loosely as "recognizing the interconnectedness of life, respecting cultural diversity and human rights, advocating global social justice, empathizing with suffering people around the world, seeing the world as others see it and feeling a sense of moral responsibility for planet Earth."

According to Swami Muktananda (2017), the purpose of education is to facilitate the process of expansion from 'me' to 'we.' He says, "Not enough stress has been given to the fact of our interdependence, to the interconnectedness between 'me' and 'we,' to the ethical dimension, to becoming humane, to the need to excel in everything so that we can care for nature and give the best to the wider society, and not just to ourselves" (p. 1).

In Nepal, the need for good relationships is outlined in the government's educational policies. National Curriculum Framework (2007) explicitly mentions the goal of education as "to help enhance and strengthen social justice, democracy, human rights, co-existence, equity and equality" (p. 14). Further, it proposes an inclusive, localized, and bilingual curriculum. As the national objective of education, it mentions the need for

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students to 'be insightful to social equality and justice and develop conduct accordingly to help create an inclusive society" (p. 31).

In India, NCERT, in its framework, defines the purpose of education as follows. "Education has to be considered as a catalyst to promote the value of social responsibility and social consciousness among students. To stimulate in students the values of love, empathy, caring, sharing and compassion for harmonious and humane relationships" (Gulati & Pant, 2017, p. 47). It is further spelled out in the related attitudes and skills in the following manner.

Belief in the dignity and worth of all human beings, listening and communication skills, love, kindness, courtesy, generosity, humility, caring and sharing, compassion, empathy; love for family, society, country, nature, and humanity as a whole; trust, gratitude, forgiveness, non-violent ways of conflict resolution, respect for others, affirmation of others' positive qualities; the joy of giving, altruism (p. 48).

Nikolakaki (2012) fears the tendency to replace human quality with human quantity, especially after the rise of capitalism. He is afraid that human values like "sense of compassion, love, solidarity, generosity, altruism" are slowly fading away in human society. He advises that it is time for us to arrest the erosion of such values through our pedagogical practices. "We must think of ways to pedagogically contribute to the creation of a human being who reflects social solidarity and responsibility, and who is more humane, with a sense of autonomy and dignity that negates every dehumanizing practice" (p. 393).

For a long time, many mathematics educators did not consider imparting values a part of their teaching-learning. According to Bishop (1999), changing such a perception was the biggest challenge. However, educating the heart became the concern of many mathematics educators eventually. Mathematics being a crucial subject in the progress of the human species, it was important for mathematics educators to ensure that those learning mathematics did not confine their knowledge to the mind level.

The ethical and moral dimension in mathematics teaching-learning has been talked about by many of late. Falkenberg (2006) believes that all subject matter should contribute to moral education and thus "curricular teaching of mathematics to engage in imaginative explorations of their moral concepts and metaphors" (p. 50). As part of a humanized mathematics education, Falkenberg talks about the mathematization of life experiences. He has this to say, "Rather than choosing areas or issues that are neutral with respect to human moral functioning, opportunities can be created for students to engage in an imaginative exploration of their prototypical moral concepts and moral metaphors within this teaching of the mathematization of life experiences" (p. 53).

Noted philosopher of mathematics Paul Ernest (2009) believes that social constructivism entails the education of the heart. He argues,

Thus, an outcome of social constructivism as a philosophy of mathematics is that questions of inter-human relations and ethics cannot be avoided and must be addressed. What is now needed, I wish to

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claim, is an ethics of mathematics, one which acknowledges the social responsibility of mathematics and how it is implicated in the great issues of freedom, justice, trust, and fellowship. It is not that this need follows logically from social constructivism. It follows morally (p. 9).

Atweh and Brady (2009) are two other researchers who propagate the discourse of ethics in mathematics education. Paraphrasing Noddings, they say that "The challenge is not only to produce competent mathematicians and mathematics users but to promote the growth of students as competent, caring, loving and lovable people" (p. 269). They talk about an ethical response-ability in the teaching-learning of mathematics. For them, responsibility is "the ability to respond to the demands of our own well-being and the demands of the others" (p. 269). Taking an ethical approach to socially responsible mathematics, they believe that we can take students beyond the utilitarian and form them into active citizens who not only read but also make attempts to transform the world with mathematics (p. 274).

Boylan (2016) considers four ethical dimensions of mathematics education. "They are relationships with others, the societal and cultural, the ecological and the self" (p. 2). Cibulskaitė (2013) is another person who brings in the relationship to others as part of the humanization of mathematics. While talking about the humanization of mathematics in the Lithuanian context, he brings out the need of "introducing students to the context of humanistic manifestations (e.g., sensitivity, openness, dignity, and responsibility)" (p. 136). He further adds that it is important to create a "learning environment and atmosphere based on respect, self-esteem, sincerity, and trust; fostering students' respect, self-esteem, sensitiveness, honesty, responsibility, and volunteering" (p. 137).

D'Ambrosio (1998) talks about how mathematics educators should take responsibility for building a peaceful society. "I do see mathematics playing an important role in achieving the high humanitarian ideals of a new civilization with equity, justice and dignity for the entire human species without distinction of race, gender, beliefs and creeds, nationalities, and cultures" (p. 67). He holds mathematics highly responsible for the disturbances in the world. He emphasizes the triangular interdependence of individuals, nature, and others and the need for mutual cooperation and respect. "This is the essence of the ethics of diversity: respect for the other (the different); solidarity with the other; cooperation with the other. This is a sure road to quality of life and dignity for all mankind." He urges mathematics educators "to give some thought to the role of mathematics education in achieving a better social order and more dignifying quality of life." It is not enough to instill in students "attitudes of rigor, precision, and correctness" (p. 71).

In a later article, D'Ambrosio (2007) comes down heavily on mathematicians and mathematics educators for ignoring their role in building a better society. "For mathematicians, priority is to publish their research in the best journals and for math educators, to propose, theorize and publish methods, which supposedly help teachers to better prepare their students to pass the variety of tests which are imposed on them. And sameness prevails!" (p. 26). He recommends the practices of ethnomathematics in classrooms to promote the values of respect for others, solidarity, cooperation, and ultimately "building up a civilization free of turbulence, arrogance, intolerance, discrimination, inequity, bigotry and hatred" (p. 34).

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Many mathematics educators have taken up the idea of mathematics and social justice as essential in the proper teaching-learning of mathematics. Prominent among them are Gutstein and Gutierrez. Gutierrez (2013) talks about the sociopolitical turn in mathematics teaching-learning and the need to embrace it to focus on the issues of identity and power that exist both in the teaching-learning of mathematics as well as in society. I believe that social justice can be achieved only when we promote values of love, compassion, generosity, and inclusiveness through mathematical concepts.

Based on Freire's revolutionary ideas on pedagogy and the purpose of education, Gutstein (2003) developed the three pedagogical goals of mathematics for social justice as 'reading the world with mathematics, writing the world with mathematics, and developing positive cultural and social identities.' It means to use mathematics 1) to understand the disparities, power structures, and inequities that exist in society, 2) to change such situations, and 3) to ground teaching-learning practices to the students' multi-contexts and help them to face life properly. Here is an excellent example of reading the world with mathematics, as I discovered.

It was the year 2001. The month of September rolled in without anything special. Then September 11 happened, and many things changed all over the world. We were all horrified by the incident and hailed the American action against the evildoers known as the 'Operation Infinite Justice.' It was a very attractive name for a mathematics student like me interested in liberation theology and talked about justice a lot. Soon I came to know that the name not only attracted but also betrayed.

A month later, I read Arundhati Roy's article, The Algebra of Infinite Justice (Outlook, 8 October, 2001). Again, a very attractive title for a mathematics and liberation theology student! It opened my eyes and thinking to a different perspective altogether. Besides the many other points that she makes, this stuck in my head. "The sophistry and fastidious algebra of Infinite Justice. How many dead Iraqis will it take to make the world a better place? How many dead Afghans for every dead American? How many dead women and children for every dead man? How many dead mujahideen for each dead investment banker?" Should not I see the connection? Algebra – Infinite – Justice! Should not all mathematics teachers and students see the connection?

The answer to the above questions must be mathematical and in numbers. But are they just mathematical and numbers? If so, what mathematical answer (number) would be the right one? Who decides what answer is right? Can there be a right answer at all?

I was very much fascinated by the way Arundhati made her point. Her strong convictions and her courage to stand up for them slowly began to influence my thinking as well. The mathematics in her article strengthened her arguments and enabled my mathematical brain to be more convinced. More importantly, I noticed how she used mathematics to show the gravity of injustice and social anomaly that was concealed in the title of the operation.

Citizenship education in the context of school mathematics is promoted by Simmt (2001). He concludes his article in this manner. "Teaching students to identify and pose problems, to explain themselves in terms

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others can understand and to question the invisible structures of mathematics is key to developing informed, active and critical citizens" (p. 6). Likewise, Beista (2009) talks about the *subjectification* function of education, of becoming a subject for the formation of the individual. While talking about the opportunities that are available in mathematics for *subjectification*, he says, "We might explore the moral possibilities of mathematics – e.g., by treating division in relation to sharing or to questions about fairness and justice – and, through this, use the potential of mathematics to contribute to *subjectification*" (p. 10).

Lancaster (2006) outlines the framework for values in mathematics for Australian schooling. Many of the nine values he talks about are directly related to students' relationships with others. They are

- Respect – *treat others with consideration and regard, respect another person's point of view or perspective,*
- Understanding tolerance and inclusion – *be aware of others and their cultures, accept diversity within a democratic society, being included and including others*
- Fair go – *pursue and protect the common good where all people are treated fairly for a just society*
- Honesty and Trustworthiness – *be honest, sincere, and seek the truth*
- Integrity – *act in accordance with principles of moral and ethical conduct, ensure consistency between words and deeds*
- Care and compassion – *care for self and others*
- Responsibility – *be accountable for one's own actions, resolve differences in constructive non-violent, and peaceful ways, contribute to society and to civic life, take care of the environment* (p. 1).

The above statements clearly indicate that mathematics teaching-learning should take a person's relationship with others seriously and promote it by imparting human values through mathematical concepts resulting in the education of the heart of the learners.

A professor of mathematics at the University of Michigan, Halpern (2016), talks about embracing three Gs in her mathematics class; "Grades, Growth and Greater Good." She goes on to explain, "This means we celebrate not only high exam scores but also the intellectual and personal growth that stems from grappling with a challenge like calculus, a growth that will serve us well whether we become engineers, poets, or diplomats. And if our journey takes on meaning beyond ourselves, then we honor that achievement, too." She believes in the teaching of mathematics as a way to enable students to go beyond themselves.

The above references indicate that education in general and mathematics education, in particular, has been concerned about the fundamental relationship of a human being to others and the education of the heart. The need to promote the right relationship with others is all the more paramount considering the number of negativities that have affected human society in the form of inequality, injustice, violence, disparities, and exclusion. Most people agree that education has a transforming power that can heal/reduce these negativities and promote communal harmony and human solidarity. In order to achieve such a transforming power, education has to promote fundamental human values through teaching-learning practices. Imparting values should not be confined to moral education classes alone but must be part of every subject. Since mathematics

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has a significant role in all the development activities of humanity, teaching-learning mathematics carries a bigger responsibility in promoting the values mentioned by the various authors above.

Some Experiments

I started teaching mathematics in the year 1999. I began my teaching pretty much the same way as I was taught mathematics in my younger days. My classes were effective for those who were interested and sound in the mathematical concepts, which would be only a minute percentage of the class, the so-called first benchers. My classes initially did not have much connection to the context outside the textbooks and syllabus. They were all about learning and memorizing formulas, following the prescribed steps, solving the given problems, and getting the solution the way I wanted it. Then the following happened.

The lesson I was dealing with was on Sets. I had prepared for my class well. I had enough familiar examples of Sets, the various ways of defining Sets, conditions to make Sets, and so on. I also had several activities for students' participation. Everything was going well until one student got up and asked me this question. "Sir, what is the use of Sets in real life?" I was not prepared for such a question. After the initial surprise, I started mumbling what I thought would satisfy the student. I mentioned how things and numbers were classified, put together, how they can be used for data collection, and whatnot. I wanted to close the discussion with a trademark statement, "You will learn more about it later."

However, the student had something else in his mind. He wanted to know how relevant the topic on Sets was for his life. He wanted to know how it could be used in other areas of life. He was from a family that ran a business and eventually would go on to take up the family business. Honestly speaking, I did not have an answer to his question. But I was determined to find out how the concept of Sets can be connected to the daily lives of ordinary people. By the time the chapter was getting over, an idea had emerged in my mind.

I realized that the notion of Sets could be connected to inclusion and exclusion in society. As I started playing with this idea in my mind, I realized that in the context of South Asia, where exclusion was prevalent in many forms like gender, ethnicity, caste, and geography, the notion of Sets could be used to teach students the value of inclusion. I wanted to try it out in class. I defined Sets where students came together from various castes, ethnicity, or other disparities. After they came together as small Sets, I told them how one could look at inclusion and exclusion as human-defined. If we defined it differently, any exclusion could be avoided. It all depended on how we looked at others and whether we wanted to include them or not. This was interesting for the students. The particular student who asked the question was happy that Sets did have some relevance to his life beyond scoring marks in the examination.

During the later years of my teaching, I began to consider other mathematics topics along similar lines. I explored how I could educate the heart of my learners by connecting mathematical topics to various values. The following are some examples of my attempts.

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Table 1 My experiments of connecting mathematics teaching-learning to values

Topics	Values
Circle	Equality, using the example of a round-table conference
Sets	Inclusiveness, respect for others, sense of belonging
Pie chart	Sharing, concern for others
Profit and loss	Honesty and integrity
Time and work	Punctuality and work ethics, hard work
Binary numbers	Binary aspects of life like good and evil, death and life, joy and sorrow
Reading the clock	Punctuality
Equations and inequalities	Equality, equity, disparities
Unitary method	Cooperation, teamwork
Formulae	Importance of following rules and regulations, following the right path
Functions and relations	Proper relationships, input and output
Fractions	Sensitivity towards others
Area and volume	Civic sense, quantity vs. quality
Interest	Exploiting others by money lenders
Various types of angles	Respecting the perspective of others
Statistics	Correct interpretation and truthfulness through data, stories behind data
Distance and time	Respect for traffic rules, saving fuel
Discount, buying, selling	Value of money, respect for parents' efforts
Slop and Tangent, Trigonometry	Inclusion while talking about ramps for the disabled

Conclusion

Mathematics teaching-learning can be and must be connected to a person's relationship with others. Educating the heart by imparting humane values through mathematical topics in classrooms is an effective way to do it. Values like generosity, inclusiveness, sensitivity, honesty, justice, respect, love, and compassion can be integrated into mathematics teaching-learning if we genuinely desire to address the issues plaguing human society, promote the well-being of all. My conviction is that mathematics teaching-learning can definitely make a difference in reducing the negativities in and around us if we impart these values in and through our mathematics classes. Since my teaching was mainly in high school classes, I have cited examples from topics I taught there. However, I believe that with some effort, any mathematics topic can be connected to values that promote the right relationship with others and thus educate the heart of the students. Such efforts can usher in the transformation of oneself, learners, and build a community that practices understanding, loving-kindness, and mindful living.

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